

MULTISENSORY INSTRUCTION (MSI): AN APPROACH IN ENHANCING NUMERACY SKILLS FOR CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the effectiveness of Multisensory Instruction (MSI) in enhancing numeracy skills among children with autism by examining the lived experiences of teachers in Camarines Norte. Using a qualitative, phenomenological approach, data were gathered through in-depth interviews and analyzed thematically with NVivo software. Findings revealed that MSI, which integrates visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic elements, significantly improves engagement, comprehension, and skill retention by aligning with students' sensory preferences and cognitive styles. Teachers emphasized the effectiveness of hands-on materials, structured routines, and digital tools in making abstract mathematical concepts more concrete. Observation-based assessment emerged as the primary evaluation method, with real-time monitoring and structured rubrics playing a crucial role in measuring progress. Additionally, the study introduced "A+SLIDES," a digital intervention that enhances numeracy skills through interactive, multisensory learning. The study concludes that MSI is an effective instructional approach for fostering numeracy development in children with autism, reducing learning barriers, and promoting inclusive education. Based on these findings, recommendations include professional development for educators, investment in MSI resources, and further research on its long-term impact across different educational settings.

Keywords: *Multisensory Instruction (MSI), numeracy skills, children with autism, Special Education, teaching strategies, assessment, skill enhancement*

INTRODUCTION

Providing quality education and support to children diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) has become a growing global concern. According to the World Health Organization (2022), about 1 in 160 children are affected by autism, making it a significant public health and educational issue worldwide. Educational interventions tailored to the unique needs of these learners have gained prominence in recent years. For instance, Lämsä et al. (2018) highlighted the potential of educational games to support individuals with learning disabilities, particularly in reading and mathematics, and emphasized the importance of effective game design in enhancing learning experiences. In another study, Morsanyi et al. (2018) explored specific learning disorders in mathematics (SLDM), revealing its widespread occurrence among primary school children and highlighting the equal prevalence across genders. These studies underscore the pressing need for more inclusive and effective instructional strategies, especially in foundational subjects like numeracy.

In the Philippines, the challenge is no less evident. Despite initiatives promoting inclusive education, children with autism often face significant barriers to acquiring basic numeracy skills, which are essential for academic achievement and everyday functioning. The integration of assistive technologies (AT), such as interactive multimedia tools and educational applications, has been shown to enhance the learning experiences of learners with special educational needs (LSEs), including those with autism (Campado et al., 2023). However, issues such as limited access to resources and ongoing technological challenges hinder their widespread implementation. Furthermore, teachers' confidence and competence in inclusive education practices significantly impact how they manage the behavioral, social, and communication difficulties of children with autism. As noted by Cahapay (2022), professional development and institutional support are crucial in empowering teachers to respond effectively to the needs of these learners.

Locally, in Camarines Norte, like many other provinces in the Philippines, children with autism encounter significant hurdles in obtaining high-quality education. Despite initiatives by the local government and schools to advocate for inclusive education, these children often struggle due to the lack of specialized resources and support available to them. The distinct cultural and socioeconomic context of the province emphasized even more the significance of researching multisensory instruction (MSI) as a strategy for improving the numeracy abilities of autistic children. Similar to other provinces in the Philippines, Camarines Norte might not have easy access to specialists with training in autism intervention and specialized educational services. As a result, investigating educators teaching strategies like MSI becomes even more crucial to guaranteeing that kids with autism in the province have fair access to education.

Teachers in Camarines Norte increasingly encounter challenges in addressing the numeracy difficulties of students diagnosed with autism. With 61 students identified across various elementary and high schools in the province for the school year 2024-2025, the struggle to develop foundational numeracy skills has become a prevailing concern among teachers. Assessments reveal that majority of these students perform

below expected proficiency levels in counting, number recognition, and basic operations. This phenomenon highlights the urgent need for innovative instructional strategies, as educators strive to bridge learning disparities and provide meaningful support tailored to the unique learning needs of children with autism.

In response to these challenges, the researchers of this study recognized the need to explore innovative instructional strategies that could address the specific learning needs of children with autism. Multisensory instruction (MSI), which involves engaging multiple senses (e.g., visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic) in the learning process, has shown promise in enhancing engagement and retention among students with diverse learning profiles. However, while anecdotal evidence and theoretical support for MSI exist, there remains a lack of empirical research specifically validating its effectiveness in improving numeracy skills among children with autism, especially in the Philippine context.

Hence, this study seeks to bridge this gap by exploring multisensory instruction in enhancing the numeracy skills of children with autism. By generating evidence-based insights, it aims to equip teachers and educational officials with practical strategies to create more inclusive and effective learning environments. Ultimately, the findings will address the current research-practice gap in special education within the Filipino context and contribute to the advancement of educational policies and interventions that support the academic success and overall well-being of children with autism at both local and global levels.

Research Questions

This study sought to explore the role of multisensory instruction in enhancing numeracy skills among children diagnosed with autism. To address this research objective, the researcher has formulated the following specific research questions:

1. What is the nature of multisensory instruction used by the teachers to enhance the numeracy skills of the students along:
 - 1.1 teaching strategies; and
 - 1.2 assessment?
2. How do children diagnosed with autism actively engage with multisensory instructional techniques when acquiring numeracy skills?
3. How do teachers utilize multisensory instruction for the development of their students' numeracy skills?
4. Based on the findings of this study, what intervention may be proposed to facilitate the enhancement of numeracy skills among children with autism through the implementation of multisensory instruction?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design using a phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences and perceptions of teachers working with children diagnosed with autism. The phenomenological method was chosen because of its emphasis on personal experiences and how individuals make meaning of those experiences (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Through in-depth interviews, the researchers aimed to uncover how teachers perceive and apply multisensory instruction and how it affects the numeracy development of their learners.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Camarines Norte, a province in the Bicol Region of the Philippines. The participants were selected from different schools in both urban and rural areas within this province. The specific names of the institutions are withheld due to the absence of formal consent for disclosure.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The target population consisted of teachers assigned to classes with learners diagnosed with autism. A total of ten (10) teachers participated in the study. These teachers were selected using purposive sampling, a non-probability technique that allows the deliberate selection of individuals with specific characteristics relevant to the study. The inclusion criteria ensured that participants had direct experience implementing multisensory strategies in teaching numeracy skills to children with autism. The distribution of participants was as follows:

School A: 5 teachers
School B: 2 teachers
School C: 2 teachers
School D: 1 teacher

This distribution allowed the researchers to ensure diversity in experiences and perspectives across various contexts.

Description of the Participants

All respondents were practicing teachers who had experience teaching learners diagnosed with autism. They had varied years of teaching experience and came from different school environments (urban and rural). While detailed demographics such as age and years of experience are not disclosed for confidentiality, all participants were from schools offering Special Education (SPED) programs and met the criteria of having implemented multisensory strategies in teaching numeracy.

Research Instrument

The main research instrument was a researcher-made interview guide designed to explore the experiences of teachers regarding the use of multisensory instruction in numeracy. The guide included three primary research questions, each broken down into several sub-questions:

- RQ1 (Teaching strategies): 6 questions
- RQ1 (Assessment techniques): 5 questions
- RQ2: 6 questions
- RQ3: 4 questions

The guide was validated by the Education Program Supervisor (EPS) in Special Education from the Division Office and two Special Education (SPED) professors from Mabini Colleges. Their feedback ensured the content validity of the instrument. Adjustments were made based on their recommendations to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study's objectives.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers began by identifying and inviting eligible participants. Each participant was presented with a consent form explaining the purpose, procedures, risks, and voluntary nature of participation. Upon receiving signed consent, the In-Depth Interviews (IDI) were scheduled.

Each interview lasted 20 to 30 minutes and was conducted face-to-face in a quiet setting. The interviews were recorded (with consent), and the researchers also took field notes. The interviews aimed to gather personal insights and rich narratives related to the participants' use of multisensory instruction in numeracy teaching.

All collected data were stored securely, and the identities of participants were anonymized in any reports or publications resulting from the study.

Data Analysis Procedure

The thematic analysis approach by Braun and Clarke (2006) was used to analyze the qualitative data. The process involved the following steps:

1. Familiarization – The researcher transcribed and reviewed all interview data.
2. Coding – Meaningful segments of data were identified and labeled.
3. Theme Development – Similar codes were grouped into potential themes.
4. Reviewing and Refining Themes – Themes were checked against the original data to ensure alignment and clarity.
5. Defining and Naming Themes – Final themes were named to reflect their content accurately.
6. Reporting – Themes were used to form the basis of the discussion and findings.

To enhance reliability and organization, NVivo software (QSR International, 2020) was utilized during the coding and theme generation stages.

Scope and Limitations

This study focused specifically on teachers in Camarines Norte who had experience teaching learners diagnosed with autism and implementing multisensory instruction in numeracy. It did not cover other subject areas or students with other types of disabilities. The number of participants (10) may limit the generalizability of the findings, but the depth and richness of the qualitative data compensate for this limitation. Additionally, as this is a phenomenological study, the results represent subjective experiences and should be interpreted within the context of qualitative inquiry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nature of Multisensory Instruction Used by Teachers to Enhance Numeracy Skills of Students with Autism along Teaching Strategies and Assessment. Multisensory instruction played a vital role in developing numeracy skills among students with autism by addressing their diverse learning styles and sensory needs. This section explored the teaching strategies and assessment methods participants used to make mathematical concepts more accessible and engaging for these learners.

Teaching Strategies. Teaching numeracy skills to students with autism requires specialized strategies that accommodate their unique learning needs. Traditional teaching methods may not always be effective in engaging students with autism, as they often require structured, repetitive, and sensory-based learning experiences

Participants employed a range of multisensory teaching strategies to enhance numeracy skills, incorporating visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic elements. This method makes mathematical concepts more concrete and relatable by aligning with students' sensory preferences—for instance, physical activities such as jumping on trampolines and pedaling on stationary bikes while counting to create a more engaging learning experience. These strategies help students, especially those diagnosed with autism, actively participate in and retain mathematical concepts.

Table 1 presents the emerging themes and participant responses related to the implementation of Multisensory Instruction (MSI) in numeracy education for children with autism.

Table 1

Nature of Multisensory Instruction Used by Teachers to Enhance Numeracy Skills of Students with Autism along Teaching Strategies

Themes	Responses
Multisensory Instruction Enhances Learning	<p><i>"Ah, para sa akin Ma'am, yung multisensory instruction ay yung ano, yung isang approach na ginagamitan ng iba't ibang senses katulad na nga Ma'am ng paningin, pandinig, paghawak ano Ma'am para mas maging engaging at accessible ang pagtuturo. Sa numeracy naman, halimbawa, gumagamit kami ng blocks, songs, at movement activities para gawing mas interesting sa mga bata."</i></p> <p>- For me, Ma'am, multisensory instruction is an approach that uses various senses like sight, hearing, and touch to make teaching more engaging and accessible. In numeracy, for example, we use blocks, songs, and movement activities to make it more interesting for the kids. – Participant 9</p>
	<p><i>"Para sa akin, ang Multisensory Instruction ay paggamit ng iba't ibang sensory inputs upang matulungan ang mga bata na maunawaan ang numeracy concepts gamit ang mga pamamaraan na naaayon sa kanilang learning style."</i></p> <p>- To me, multisensory instruction means using a variety of sensory inputs to help children grasp numeracy concepts through methods that match their preferred learning styles — Participant 3</p>
	<p><i>"Ang multisensory approach ay tumutugon sa iba't ibang learning styles, kaya nabibigyan ang mga estudyante ng pagkakataong matuto sa paraang pinakaangkop sa kanila, maging ito man ay visual, tactile, o auditory cues."</i></p> <p>- The multisensory approach caters to different learning styles, allowing students to learn in a way that suits them best, whether it's through visual, tactile, or auditory cues – Participant 8</p>
Use of Multiple Senses in Numeracy Instruction	<p><i>"Para sa akin Ma'am, ang Multisensory Instruction sa numeracy para sa mga batang may Autism ay nangangahulugang na gawing masaya at engaging ang Math gamit ang kanilang senses. Puwede tayong gumamit ng makukulay na blocks, kumanta ng counting songs, at iba pang interactive na paraan para mas matuto sila."</i></p> <p>- Multisensory Instruction in numeracy for children with Autism means making Math fun and engaging by using all their senses, we can use colorful blocks, singing counting songs etc. – Participant 1</p>
	<p><i>"So yung multisensory instruction ay ito yung ano, yung gumagamit ng iba't ibang senses Ma'am paningin, pandinig, pandama, minsan pati galaw ng bata. Same Ma'am sa ano, sa pagtuturo ng numeracy, hindi lang kami nagpapasulat o nagpapabasa. Ayun gumagamit din kami ng mga bagay tulad ng blocks, clay, o counters para mas maipakita sa kanila ang konsepto ng numbers."</i></p> <p>- So, multisensory instruction is about using different senses like sight, hearing, touch, and sometimes movement. In teaching numeracy, we don't just focus on writing or reading but also use materials like blocks, clay, or counters to show the concept of numbers. – Participant 4</p>
Engagement and Sensory-Based Learning	<p><i>"Oo, yan yung ginagamit ang sense of touch, nahahawakan nila, sense of sight nakikita nila at iba pang senses."</i></p> <p>- Yes, it uses the sense of touch what they can feel, sight (what they can see, and other senses – Participant 10</p>
	<p><i>"Ah, multisensory instruction? Hmm, para sa akin, ito yung paggamit ng iba't ibang senses touch, sight, hearing para matulungan ang mga bata na maintindihan ang Math concepts. Halimbawa, ginagamit namin ang manipulatives, songs, at visuals para mas engaging at interactive ang pagkatuto nila."</i></p> <p>-Multisensory instruction? For me, it's about using different senses like touch, sight, and hearing to help children understand Math concepts. For example, we use manipulatives, songs, and visuals to make learning more engaging and interactive. – Participant 6</p>
	<p><i>"Nakakabuo ito ng positibo at dynamic na learning environment, kung saan na-eengganyo ang mga estudyante na tuklasin ang mga numero gamit ang galaw, paghawak, at tunog, na nagpapataas ng kanilang kumpiyansa."</i></p>

- It creates a positive and dynamic learning environment, where students feel encouraged to explore numbers through movement, touch, and sound, leading to increased confidence. – Participant 5

"Ginagamit namin ito para ihanda ang mga bata. Ang multisensory materials tulad ng visual aids ay nakakatulong upang makuha ang atensyon ng mga batang may Autism at matulungan silang matuto."

- We use it for prepping them, multisensory materials such as visual aids to catch their attention helps the students with autism to develop or learn something. – Participant 2

Flexibility and Individualized Learning

"Nakakatulong ito sa pag-alis ng sensory barriers sa pamamagitan ng pagbibigay-daan sa mga estudyante na makipag-ugnayan sa mga materyal ayon sa kanilang sariling bilis, kaya mas nagiging kumportable at angkop sa kanilang pangangailangan ang kanilang learning experience."

- It helps break down sensory barriers by allowing students to engage with materials at their own pace, providing a more comfortable and individualized learning experience that addresses their unique needs – Participant 7

The theme with the most responses is "Use of Multiple Senses in Numeracy Instruction," which highlights how integrating sight, hearing, touch, and movement helps children with autism better understand numeracy concepts.

According to the participants' responses and their definition of MSI, they said that Multisensory instruction (MSI) in numeracy combines sensory cues to make math interesting and understandable for autistic children. MSI lets teachers use colorful images, tactile manipulatives, musical elements, and sensory-friendly activities. This method makes math more engaging and active by making it concrete, multisensory, and tailored to kids' learning preferences. Participants said MSI makes learning entertaining and engaging. This adaptability benefits students with autism by respecting their sensory demands and learning styles, which standard schooling often ignores. MSI demonstrates how versatile and inclusive numeracy education can be, emphasizing sensory diversity. MSI uses sensory aspects to help students with autism learn math intuitively and meaningfully.

"So yung multisensory instruction ay ito yung ano, yung gumagamit ng iba't ibang senses Ma'am—paningin, pandinig, pandama, minsan pati galaw ng bata. Same Ma'am sa ano, sa pagtuturo ng numeracy, hindi lang kami nagpapasulat o nagpapabasa. Ayun, gumagamit din kami ng mga bagay tulad ng blocks, clay, o counters para mas maipakita sa kanila ang konsepto ng numbers." - Participant 4

(Translation: So, multisensory instruction is about using different senses like sight, hearing, touch, and sometimes movement. In teaching numeracy, we don't just focus on writing or reading but also use materials like blocks, clay, or counters to show the concept of numbers.)

Participant 4 emphasized that using colorful blocks, counting songs, clay, and counters makes learning more engaging and interactive. Instead of relying solely on writing and reading, teacher incorporate hands-on materials that allow students to physically experience mathematical concepts.

This multisensory approach ensures that children actively engage with numbers, making abstract ideas more concrete and accessible. The response suggests that using multiple senses in numeracy instruction is effective strategy for helping children, especially those with autism, grasp mathematical concepts in a way that suits their learning needs.

In Camarines Norte, where classroom resources and teaching methodologies vary across urban and rural schools, integrating multisensory learning strategies can enhance numeracy instruction, particularly for children with diverse learning needs, including those with autism. Schools in the province especially in remote areas, often face challenges such as limited access to specialized teaching materials and teacher training in inclusive education.

The findings of this study were corroborated by De Domenico et al. (2024), who emphasized the effectiveness of multisensory instruction in enhancing learning outcomes for children with autism. It highlighted the importance of engaging multiple senses—such as sight, touch, and hearing—to support numeracy instruction, thereby making abstract mathematical concepts more accessible and concrete for students with autism. The use of hands-on materials like blocks, counting songs, and tactile objects, as reported by participants in this study, mirrors the strategies discussed by De Domenico et al. (2024), they advocate for sensory-based learning approaches to improve cognitive processing and engagement.

Additionally, while the theme of "Flexibility and Individualized Learning" received minimal attention in the present study. The former study stresses the necessity of adapting instructional methods to meet the diverse sensory and cognitive needs of learners with autism, reinforcing the importance of personalized, student-centered teaching strategies.

Only one participant specifically mentioned how multisensory instruction helps break down sensory barriers by allowing students to engage with materials at their own pace. This approach allows learners to engage with educational materials in ways that align with their unique sensory preferences, thereby fostering a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

"Nakakatulong ito sa pag-alis ng sensory barriers sa pamamagitan ng pagbibigay-daan sa mga estudyante na makipag-ugnayan sa mga materyal ayon sa kanilang sariling bilis, kaya mas nagiging kumportable at angkop sa kanilang pangangailangan ang kanilang learning experience." – Participant 7

(Translation: It helps break down sensory barriers by allowing students to engage with materials at their own pace, providing a more comfortable and individualized learning experience that addresses their unique needs.)

This perspective highlights the potential for multisensory instruction to create a more comfortable and personalized learning environment, addressing the unique needs

of each student. While fewer participants mentioned this theme, its significance cannot be overlooked, as individualized learning is essential for supporting students with diverse learning needs.

This was conformed by Unwin et al. (2022) with the finding that multisensory instruction helps break down sensory barriers by allowing students to engage with materials at their own pace. Their research on Multi-Sensory Environments (MSEs) for autistic children revealed that when students had control over sensory stimuli, they exhibited increased attention, reduced sensory-related behaviors, and improved engagement.

This supports Participant 7 perspective that multisensory instruction creates a more comfortable learning environment by allowing students to interact with materials based on their sensory preferences. It was also found that autonomy over sensory input helped reduce sensory overload, enabling students to focus better and process information more effectively. Their study underscores the importance of individualized sensory adjustments, emphasizing that while not all students respond to multisensory instruction in the same way, providing opportunities for self-regulation can significantly enhance learning outcomes and overall comfort in educational settings.

Assessment. Assessing the numeracy skills of students with autism requires a thoughtful and adaptive approach that accommodates their unique cognitive and sensory processing differences. Conventional assessment methods, such as standardized tests and written evaluations, may not effectively capture the true mathematical abilities of students with autism, as these approaches often rely on rigid structures that may not align with their learning preferences. Many students with autism struggle with conventional testing formats due to difficulties with communication, attention, or anxiety, which can impact their performance and fail to reflect their actual understanding of mathematical concepts.

Assessment in multisensory instruction involves both checklist and observation methods that track student progress. Participants use hands-on activities with manipulatives and visual aids to monitor understanding and retention, ensuring students consistently apply their learning. Feedback and observation during these activities allow participants to assess comprehension and adapt teaching methods as needed. Assessment plays a crucial role in evaluating the effectiveness of multisensory instruction in numeracy education for children with autism. By utilizing a combination of observation, checklists, rubrics, and students' response, teachers can monitor progress and adapt their instructional approaches to meet individual learning needs.

Table 2 presents the key themes and participant responses on assessment methods used to evaluate the effectiveness of multisensory instruction in numeracy education. In the analysis of assessment methods for multisensory instruction in numeracy education, the theme "Observation-Based Assessment" emerged as the most frequently mentioned by participants. They emphasized the importance of direct

observation to evaluate students' application of numeracy skills acquired through multisensory approaches.

"Ine-aassess ko ang pagiging effective yun sa pamamagitan ng pag-oobserve ng improvements sa pagawa ng mga gawain, tulad ng pagbilang o pagsasaayos, para makita kung consistent na ina-apply ng mga estudyante ang numeracy skills na natutunan nila gamit ang multisensory methods." - Participant 1

(Translation: I will assess its effectiveness by observing improvements in performing tasks, such as counting or organizing, to see if the students consistently apply the numeracy skills they have learned through multisensory methods.)

The efficacy of multisensory education can be evaluated by monitoring enhancements in task execution, such as counting or sorting, as indicated by Participant 1. This method is significant since it shows pupils' consistent application of numeracy skills. These tasks help teachers identify student comprehension strengths and shortcomings, allowing them to adjust their teaching methods. Students' ability to perform these challenges shows they understand the principles and boosts their confidence and motivation to participate in numeracy activities.

Table 2

Nature of Multisensory Instruction Used by Teachers to Enhance Numeracy Skills of Students with Autism along Assessment

Themes	Responses
	<p><i>"Ine-aassess ko ang pagiging effective yun sa pamamagitan ng pag-oobserve ng improvements sa pagawa ng mga gawain, tulad ng pagbilang o pagsasaayos, para makita kung consistent na ina-apply ng mga estudyante ang numeracy skills na natutunan nila gamit ang multisensory methods."</i></p> <p>- I assess effectiveness by observing improvements in task completion, such as counting or sorting, to see if students are consistently applying numeracy skills learned through multisensory methods. – Participant 1</p>
Observation-Based Assessment	<p><i>"Ginagamit ko ang observation at checklist para i-monitor ang engagement at kung paano nila ina-apply ang multisensory techniques."</i></p> <p>- I use observations and checklists to monitor engagement and application of multisensory techniques. – Participant 5</p> <p><i>"Sa assessment, gumagamit ako ng hands-on activities at observation. Tinitingnan ko kung paano nila ginagamit ang manipulatives sa pagbilang."</i></p> <p>- In the assessment, I use hands-on activities and observation. I check how they use manipulatives for counting. - Participant 6</p>
Observation-Based Assessment	<p><i>"Observation. Oo, gumagamit kami ng rubrics. Oo Ma'am, nabanggit na namin ang rubrics noon. Halimbawa, kung oral task ang gagamitin, may rubrics kami. Kung may ino-observerbahang specific abilities, may rubrics din kami."</i></p> <p>- Observation. Yes, we use rubrics. Yes, Ma'am, we mentioned rubrics before. For example, if you're using oral tasks, you have rubrics. If you're observing specific abilities, you also use rubrics. - Participant 3</p>

	<p><i>"Gumagamit kami ng checklist. Parang grading system nila yun, tulad ng isang checklist."</i> - "We use a checklist. It serves as their grading system, like a checklist." - Participant 2</p>
Checklist and Rubric-Based Evaluation	<p><i>"Madalas, kapag gumagawa ako ng assessment, isinasama ko rin ang practical tasks at real-world applications para makita kung na-master na nila ang numeracy skills."</i> - Usually, by making an assessment, I also include practical tasks and real-world applications for demonstrating number skill master. - Participant 7 <i>"Ang feedback ng mga estudyante habang gumagawa ng hands-on activities, tulad ng paggamit ng manipulatives, ay nagpapakita kung gaano nila naiintindihan at naaalala ang mga konsepto, kaya nagbibigay ito ng insight sa epekto ng multisensory instruction."</i> - Feedback from students during hands-on activities, like using manipulatives, indicates how well they comprehend and retain concepts, providing insight into the lasting impact of multisensory instruction." Participant 4</p>
Student Feedback and Engagement	<p><i>"Para mabigyan agad ng feedback ang mga estudyante tungkol sa pagkakaintindi nila sa mga konsepto, sinasabi na agad ang mga kailangan iimprove."</i> - To provide immediate feedback on student understanding of concepts. You'll state the areas for improvement" - Participant 10</p>
Adjustments and Modifications for Individual Needs	<p><i>"Nakakatulong ito sa pag-adjust ng pagtuturo para masigurong epektibo pa rin ang multisensory approach para sa lahat ng estudyante."</i> - "Informs adjustments to instruction, ensuring that the multisensory approach remains effective for all students." - Participant 8 <i>"Nagbibigay kami ng modifications batay sa sensory processing needs ng bawat estudyante para masigurong patas ang assessment ng kanilang numeracy abilities."</i> - "Providing modifications for specific sensory processing needs to ensure fair evaluations of numeracy abilities." - Participant 9</p>

Another participant highlighted the use of observations and checklists to monitor engagement and the practical application of multisensory techniques.

"Gumagamit kami ng checklist. Parang grading system nila yun, tulad ng isang checklist."
 - Participant 2

(Translation: We use a checklist. It serves as their grading system, like a checklist)

Teachers can assess pupils' knowledge retention and application by reviewing previous material. Continuous evaluation helps pupils enhance their skills by ensuring permanent and foundational learning. Practice and reinforcement are crucial for numeracy mastery. However, Participant 4 believes pupil input during manipulative-based practical assignments is essential for comprehension and memory.

The findings of this study were corroborated by Huda et al. (2024), which emphasized the significance of observation-based assessments in evaluating children with autism. The study highlighted that direct observation remains a crucial tool for assessing engagement, learning progress, and the effectiveness of instructional approaches tailored to children with autism. Similarly, in the present study, participants predominantly relied on real-time observation to gauge how well students applied numeracy skills acquired through multisensory instruction. Additionally, both studies suggest that individualized modifications are essential in assessment strategies to accommodate diverse sensory processing needs. However, the limited emphasis on adjustments in the current study mirrors a gap identified by Huda et al. (2024), who

advocate for more inclusive and adaptive evaluation methods to ensure fair and effective assessments for all students with autism.

These insights underscore the value participants place on real-time observation to gauge student progress and the effectiveness of instructional strategies.

Conversely, the theme "Adjustments and Modifications for Individual Needs" received the least attention, with only two participants referencing it. One participant discussed informing adjustments to instruction to ensure the multisensory approach remains effective for all students, while another emphasized providing modifications for specific sensory processing needs to ensure fair evaluations of numeracy abilities. This limited focus suggests that while some educators recognize the necessity of tailoring instruction to individual sensory needs, it may not be a widespread practice or priority in current assessment methods.

These findings are supported by De La Cruz (2020), who emphasized the customization of multisensory techniques to meet individual students' needs, demonstrating significant improvements in engagement and reading performance. This aligns with the theme of "Adjustments and Modifications for Individual Needs," as it highlights the importance of tailoring instruction to accommodate diverse sensory processing needs.

In the context of Camarines Norte, where schools cater to learners with varying backgrounds and resources, implementing customized multisensory strategies can significantly improve student engagement and comprehension. Many schools in the province, particularly in rural areas, face challenges such as limited access to specialized learning materials and training for inclusive education.

Active Engagement of Children Diagnosed with Autism with Multisensory Instruction in Acquiring Numeracy Skills. Children diagnosed with autism engage actively with multisensory instruction by interacting with diverse sensory materials that resonate with their learning preferences. By integrating familiar and structured routines with engaging hands-on activities, MSI minimizes learning barriers and enhances confidence among children with autism. The incorporation of digital tools and interactive resources further supports individualized learning needs, making mathematics a more accessible and enjoyable subject.

Understanding how students with autism actively engage with these techniques is essential in determining their effectiveness in numeracy instruction. Some children respond well to visual aids such as number charts, diagrams, and digital applications that provide clear, structured representations of mathematical concepts.

Others benefit from kinesthetic and tactile experiences, such as manipulating physical objects (e.g., counting blocks, abacus, or sensory trays) to build a concrete understanding of numbers and operations. Auditory strategies, including rhythmic counting, songs, and verbal reinforcement, may also help reinforce learning for some

autism learners. By catering to the diverse sensory preferences of autism learners, multisensory instruction fosters a more inclusive and supportive learning environment.

Table 3 presents key themes and participant responses on how autism learners respond to multisensory instruction in numeracy education.

Table 3

Active Engagement of Children Diagnosed with Autism with Multisensory Instruction in Acquiring Numeracy Skills

Themes	Responses
Preference for Multisensory and Manipulative Learning	<p><i>"Ang mga batang may autism ay madalas na mas epektibong natututo gamit ang multisensory approach, lalo na kapag may kasamang visual aids at tactile experiences. Mas gusto nila ang visual learning. Halimbawa, gumagamit kami ng play dough para ipakita ang mga numero. Napaka-engaged niya sa pagbibilang at paghulma ng dough na hindi niya napansin na natututo na pala siya."</i></p> <p>- Autism learners often respond well to multisensory approaches, especially those that involve visual aids and tactile experiences. They often have a strong preference for visual learning. We often use play dough to represent numbers, he was so engaged counting and shaping the dough that he did not even realize that he was learning.</p> <p>- Participant 1</p>
	<p><i>"Mas gusto ng mga batang may autism ang manipulative materials kaysa sa pagsusulat."</i></p> <p>- Autism learners like manipulative materials instead of writing. - Participant 2</p> <p><i>"Mahilig sila sa puzzles, clay, blocks, at counters. Tuwing nagpapakita ako ng bagong materials, lahat sila ay attentive."</i></p> <p>- They love puzzles, clay, blocks, and counters. Every time I show them new materials, they are all attentive. - Participant 10</p>
Increased Engagement and Positive Response to Multisensory Learning	<p><i>"Mas nakakapag-focus at mas nagpa-participate ang maraming estudyante kapag may tactile o visual elements sa lesson, kasi mas nagiging concrete ang learning para sa kanila."</i></p> <p>- "Many students show increased focus and participation when tactile or visual elements are included, as it makes learning feel more concrete. - Participant 6</p>
	<p><i>"Sobrang excited sila, very positive, at gustong-gusto nila. Mas marami silang natutunan kumpara sa traditional na paraan ng pagtuturo. Nababawasan din ang boredom nila, kasi pakiramdam nila ay naglalaro lang sila imbes na natuturuan."</i></p> <p>- They are very excited about it, very positive, and they love it. They learn more compared to actual or traditional teaching methods. It lessens their boredom, to be honest, because they don't think they are being taught; rather, they think they are playing. - Participant 3</p>
Increased Engagement and Positive Response to Multisensory Learning	<p><i>:"Napapansin ko na mas masigasig at engaged sila kapag ginagamit ang preferred sensory methods nila sa lesson, tulad ng musika o activities na may touch-based interaction."</i></p> <p>- I find out that they are more enthusiastic and engaged when lessons incorporate their preferred sensory methods, like music or touch-based activities." Participant 4</p>
	<p><i>"Kung ikukumpara sa paggamit lang ng papel at lapis, mas nag-eejoy ang mga bata sa pag-aaral. Sa totoo lang, mas nag-improve ang ASD learners. Tulad ng sinabi ko, mas engaged sila, at base sa records namin, mas tumaas ang kanilang skills."</i></p> <p>- Compared to using just paper and pencil only, the kids enjoy learning. The ASD has improved, to be honest. Like what I said, they are more engaged, and based on our records, their skills have leveled up." -Participant 7</p>

Routine, Familiarity, and Structured Learning	"Kapag nakita nila ang materials, dahil sanay sila sa routine, agad silang nae-excite, nakikinig, at sumusunod sa akin kapag nagbibigay ako ng instructions." - If they see the materials, since they have a routine, they get easily excited, they listen, and are obedient to me when I instruct something. - Participant 5
Technology and Digital Tools for Engagement	"Kapag gumagamit ng multimedia, lalo na ng mga apps na may online activities, mas nae-engganyo sila at mas nakikilahok sa lesson." - Using multimedia, especially apps with online activities, their interest is aroused, and they participate well. - Participant 9
Multisensory Learning Enhances	"Nakakatulong ito para mas maintindihan nila ang mga konsepto, manatiling engaged, at malampasan ang sensory challenges" - It helps them grasp concepts better, stay engaged, and even overcome sensory challenges.
Concept Understanding	"Nakita ko mismo kung paano nakakatulong ang paggamit ng makukulay na manipulatives at interactive games para gawing mas masaya at epektibo ang pag-aaral ng mga numero." I've seen firsthand how using colorful manipulatives and interactive games makes learning numbers fun and effective." - Participant 8

The "Preference for Multisensory and Manipulative Learning" theme received the most responses, emphasizing how autism learners benefit from hands-on and visual learning experiences. Participants highlighted that students with autism often favor visual aids and tactile experiences, such as play dough, puzzles, clay, blocks, and counters, over traditional writing methods. For instance, "Madalas naming gamitin ang play dough para ipakita ang mga numbers. Sobrang aliw sila sa pagbibilang at paglaro ng play dough, hindi nila namamalayan na natututo na pala sila." – Participant 1

(Translation: We often use play dough to show the numbers. They enjoy counting and playing with the play dough so much that they don't even realize they are learning.)

Participant 1 observed that using play dough to represent numbers kept a student so engaged that they didn't realize they were learning. Another noted that introducing new materials captured the students' attention, enhancing their focus and participation. These insights suggest that incorporating multisensory and manipulative materials can make learning more engaging and effective for students with autism.

The children with autism respond well to multisensory components and are ready for sensory-appropriate numeracy tasks. Play dough, blocks and puzzles make mathematics entertaining without pressure. MSI engages autistic children's curiosity and sensory preferences, unlike paper-based training. As pupils naturally explore mathematics, they gain numeracy knowledge and a sense of accomplishment. MSI's emphasis on active involvement creates an inclusive and engaging learning environment that helps pupils connect meaningfully with information and improve academically and socially.

Autism students need this affirmative attitude reaction since they may struggle with traditional teaching methods and lose interest when learning gets boring. MSI creates a welcoming and helpful learning environment by incorporating sensory components that meet pupils' emotional and sensory needs. The observed behavioural and emotional participation shows that MSI creates a classroom climate where pupils feel valued and motivated, boosting their academic performance and emotional health.

This was conformed by Delpont (2021), the "Preference for Multisensory and Manipulative Learning" theme by highlighting the effectiveness of math manipulatives in enhancing engagement and understanding. His study shows that hands-on learning makes abstract concepts more concrete, aligning with participants' observations that children with autism benefit from visual and tactile materials like play dough and blocks. By engaging multiple senses, multisensory instruction (MSI) keeps students motivated and reduces the pressure of traditional methods, making math more enjoyable and meaningful for autistic learners.

On the other hand, the "Routine, Familiarity, and Structured Learning" theme had the fewest responses, indicating that while important, it may not be the primary focus for educators using multisensory instruction.

"Kapag nakita nila ang materials, dahil sanay sila sa routine, agad silang nae-excite, nakikinig, at sumusunod sa akin kapag nagbibigay ako ng instructions." - Participant 5

(Translation: When they see the materials, because they are used to the routine, they get excited right away, listen, and follow me when I give instructions.)

"Kapag gumagamit ng multimedia, lalo na ng mga apps na may online activities, mas nae-engganyo sila at mas nakikilahok sa lesson." - Participant 9

(Translation: When using multimedia, especially apps with online activities, they become more engaged and participate more in the lesson.)

Participants noted that when students see familiar materials, their established routines lead them to become easily excited, attentive, and obedient during instruction. This observation underscores the importance of consistency and structure in the learning environment for students with autism. While not widely discussed among participants, maintaining a predictable routine and using familiar materials can play a crucial role in facilitating effective learning for these students.

The study by Faunillan (2023) aligns with this result, as it demonstrates the effectiveness of the Multisensory Learning Approach (MLA) in improving phonological awareness among kindergarten learners. Similar to the findings in the present study, he emphasized how structured, familiar, and routine-based multisensory activities significantly enhance student engagement. The participants in the current study observed that students become excited and more attentive when presented with familiar materials and consistent instructional methods, which mirrors his findings that predictable, multisensory strategies contribute to improved learning outcomes.

Utilization of Multisensory Instruction by Teachers for Developing Students' Numeracy Skills. The development of numeracy skills is a crucial component of a child's education, as it establishes the groundwork for logical reasoning, problem-solving, and the practical application of mathematical concepts in everyday life. A strong numeracy

foundation enables students to confidently engage in mathematical thinking, preparing them for more complex learning as they progress academically.

To enhance numeracy instruction, participants employ multisensory teaching strategies that create an engaging and immersive learning environment tailored to diverse student needs. Multisensory instruction incorporates visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and tactile elements, allowing students to absorb mathematical concepts in ways that align with their preferred learning styles. By integrating sensory engagement into lessons, educators make numeracy instruction more inclusive, addressing the challenges faced by students with different cognitive abilities and learning preferences.

For instance, pairing counting songs with physical movements such as clapping, stomping, or finger gestures helps reinforce numerical patterns through both auditory and kinesthetic channels. Additionally, using colorful manipulatives such as counting blocks, textured number cards, or interactive digital tools allows students to visualize and physically interact with mathematical concepts, enhancing comprehension and retention. These techniques not only make learning more enjoyable but also provide multiple pathways for understanding, catering to students who may struggle with traditional instruction.

Table 4

Utilization of Multisensory Instruction by Teachers for Developing Students' Numeracy Skills

Themes	Responses
	<p><i>"Kapag ini-integrate ang physical activities, tulad ng number lines sa sahig, mas nararanasan ng mga estudyante ang math concepts sa pisikal na paraan, kaya mas engaging at madaling tandaan."</i></p> <p>- Integrating physical activities, like number lines on the floor, allows students to experience math concepts physically, making it more engaging and memorable.- Participant 8</p>
Physical and Movement-Based Learning	<p><i>"Ang mga counting songs na may kasamang actions ay tumutulong sa mga estudyante na maiugnay ang rhythm at movement sa counting sequences."</i></p> <p>- Counting songs paired with actions help students link rhythm and movement with counting sequences." - Participant 4</p>
Hands-On and Manipulative Learning	<p><i>"Ang pagsasadula ng word problems gamit ang props ay nakakatulong sa mga estudyante na i-translate ang abstract concepts sa mas konkretong sitwasyon."</i></p> <p>- Acting out word problems with props helps students translate abstract concepts into concrete scenarios. -Participant 1</p> <p><i>"Ang hands-on activities tulad ng paggamit ng manipulatives at pagsasadula ng math problems ay sobrang epektibo sa kanila. Kailangan lang gawing buhay ang mga numero sa pamamagitan ng touch, sight, at movement."</i></p> <p>- Hands-on activities/experiences like using manipulatives and acting out math problems are super effective for them. It's all about making numbers come alive through touch, sight, and movement. - Participant 5</p> <p><i>"Kapag gumagamit ng hands-on tools tulad ng counting blocks at textured cards, mas madaling naiintindihan ng mga estudyante ang numeracy dahil naikokonekta nila ito sa mga totoong bagay."</i></p>

	<p>- By integrating hands-on tools, like counting blocks and textured cards, students can connect abstract concepts to real-world objects, making numeracy more tangible and easier to understand. - Participant 6</p> <p><i>"Gumagamit ako ng manipulatives tulad ng base-ten blocks para sa hands-on na pag-unawa sa place value concepts."</i></p> <p>- I use manipulatives like base-ten blocks for hands-on understanding of place value concepts. - Participant 10</p> <p><i>"Pinagsasama ko ang visual presentations, verbal instructions, at tactile objects para matugunan ang iba't ibang sensory preferences at mapalalim ang kanilang pag-unawa."</i></p> <p>- I combine visual presentations with verbal instructions and tactile objects to address various sensory preferences and help deepen their understanding. - Participant 2</p>
Visual Learning Strategies	<p><i>"Ang mga visual aids tulad ng makukulay na charts ay nagpapakita ng number relationships, kaya mas nauunawaan nila ito nang mas malalim."</i></p> <p>- Visual aids like colorful charts illustrate number relationships, fostering a deeper understanding for them. - Participant 9</p> <p><i>"Kapag tinuturuan ko sila ng numeracy skills, gumagamit ako ng makukulay at mahahawakang bagay dahil mas engaging ito para sa kanila. Halimbawa, abacus."</i></p> <p>- When it comes to their numerical skills, I use objects that are colorful to their eyes and they can touch because it is more engaging. For instance, abacus." Participant 3</p>
Use of Colorful and Tactile Objects for Engagement	<p><i>"Pinagagawa ko sila ng mga hugis gamit ang straw para matutunan ang geometric concepts sa pamamagitan ng tactile exploration."</i></p> <p>- Students build shapes with straws to learn geometric concepts through tactile exploration. - Participant 7</p>

Table 4 presents key themes and participant responses regarding effective numeracy teaching strategies, emphasizing the impact of multisensory approaches. The responses highlight the benefits of incorporating sensory-rich experiences into lessons, demonstrating how such methods improve student engagement, comprehension, and overall learning outcomes.

In analyzing the responses, the theme "Physical and Movement-Based Learning" emerged as the most frequently mentioned. Participants highlighted the effectiveness of incorporating physical activities into math instruction to enhance engagement and understanding. For instance, one participant noted "Kapag ini-integrate ang physical activities, tulad ng number lines sa sahig, mas nararanasan ng mga estudyante ang math concepts sa pisikal na paraan, kaya mas engaging at madaling tandaan." - Participant 8

(Translation: Integrating physical activities, like number lines on the floor, allows students to experience math concepts physically, making it more engaging and memorable.)

Another participant mentioned that counting songs paired with actions help students link rhythm and movement with counting sequences. These insights suggest that movement-based learning strategies can make abstract mathematical concepts more concrete and accessible for students.

The study by Goya (2023) aligns with this result, as it explores the Concrete-Representational-Abstract (CRA) instructional sequence for teaching mathematical concepts to middle school students with autism. The CRA approach emphasizes hands-on, movement-based learning, which mirrors the participants' experiences in integrating

physical activities like number lines on the floor and counting songs with actions. Goya's findings demonstrate that engaging students physically in mathematical tasks enhances comprehension and retention, making abstract concepts more tangible. This directly supports the idea that movement-based learning strategies in MSI encourage active participation, improve conceptual understanding, and foster a more engaging math learning experience for students with autism.

Conversely, the theme "Use of Colorful and Tactile Objects for Engagement" received the least emphasis, with only two participants referencing it. One participant shared that they use colorful objects, like an abacus, to engage students in numerical skills, while another described how students build shapes with straws to learn geometric concepts through tactile exploration. Although less frequently mentioned, these approaches highlight the potential benefits of using visually appealing and hands-on materials to capture students' interest and facilitate learning.

While the use of colorful and tactile objects is not a primary focus among participants, it still plays a role in engaging students and supporting their learning. The examples provided indicate that incorporating visually appealing and hands-on materials can enhance students' interaction with academic concepts, particularly in mathematics and geometry. The limited emphasis on this strategy may imply that educators prioritize other instructional methods, such as individualized learning or multisensory approaches, over purely visual and tactile tools.

However, the responses also suggest that when used effectively, these materials can serve as valuable resources for reinforcing learning and making abstract concepts more concrete for students with autism.

The study aligns with Okray et al. (2023) by supporting the idea that multisensory learning enhances cognitive performance and memory retention. They found that multisensory learning binds neurons into a cross-modal memory engram, strengthening neural plasticity. Similarly, the study on teachers' utilization of multisensory instruction demonstrates how integrating movement, hands-on learning, and visual strategies improves student engagement and understanding. Both studies highlight the benefits of sensory-rich educational approaches in reinforcing learning through multiple neural pathways. Therefore, the findings complement each other, reinforcing the effectiveness of multisensory instruction in improving cognitive and academic outcomes.

Proposed Intervention for Enhancing Numeracy Skills Among Children with Autism Through Multisensory Instruction. The findings highlight the critical role of multisensory instruction (MSI) in enhancing numeracy skills among children with autism. Activities such as counting songs paired with movements, threading beads, and using tactile materials like number blocks and puzzles have demonstrated their potential to improve engagement and comprehension. However, teachers face challenges in adapting these strategies to the varying levels of autism among learners, emphasizing the need for innovative and accessible tools to ensure inclusivity and effectiveness in numeracy instruction.

The proposed intervention, "A+SLIDES: Autism Support through Learning Innovations and Digital Engagement Strategies for Numeracy," introduces user-friendly, interactive digital slides explicitly designed to enhance numeracy skills among children with autism. These slides incorporate sensory-rich elements such as animated visuals, engaging sounds, and interactive puzzles to cater to the unique learning preferences of students. With features like clickable objects, colorful number animations, and tactile exercises simulated digitally, the slides aim to make numeracy concepts more relatable and enjoyable. The tool is intuitive and straightforward, enabling teachers to use it effectively without the need for extensive training.

The A+SLIDES includes various numeracy topics designed to systematically and interactively develop foundational math skills. The slides cover counting from 1 to 10 with visual and auditory cues to enhance recognition and sequencing. They also include number-matching activities to strengthen association and pattern recognition, along with dedicated slides for each numeral to reinforce identification, pronunciation, and counting. Moreover, the inclusion of shape recognition slides introduces basic geometric concepts, encouraging sensory exploration through animated visuals.

A+SLIDES applies multisensory instructional (MSI) principles in a digital format to enhance numeracy skills among children with autism. This intervention integrates interactive slides featuring visuals, sound cues, and problem-solving exercises to support flexible, self-paced learning. While MSI is validated for numeracy development, optimizing A+SLIDES requires attention to instructional adaptability, technological affordances, and observation-based assessment.

A+SLIDES accommodates diverse learning styles—visual learners engage with animations, auditory learners benefit from synchronized sound cues, and kinesthetic learners interact with clickable objects simulating manipulatives. This adaptability allows educators to tailor instruction and adjust complexity based on student needs.

Expanding on traditional MSI methods, A+SLIDES leverages animated sequences, interactive puzzles, and auditory reinforcements to deepen engagement and comprehension. With growing digital infrastructure in regions like Camarines Norte, this scalable tool merges multisensory learning with technology to enhance numeracy instruction.

Ultimately, A+SLIDES represents a significant step toward bridging multisensory instruction and digital learning to support numeracy development among children with autism. By leveraging interactive and sensory-rich elements, it enhances engagement, comprehension, and accessibility, fostering a more inclusive learning experience. As educators continue to explore innovative teaching strategies, the adaptability and scalability of A+SLIDES offer promising opportunities for broader implementation. Moving forward, ongoing evaluation and refinement will be essential to maximize its impact, ensuring that all learners receive the support they need to build foundational numeracy skills with confidence and success.

Conclusions

The conclusions drawn from the study's findings are as follows:

1. Multisensory instruction proves to be an effective approach in teaching numeracy to children with autism by catering to diverse learning styles and sensory preferences. The integration of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic elements enhances engagement, comprehension, and skill retention. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of flexibility in instruction, allowing students to interact with learning materials in a way that best suits their cognitive and sensory needs. While MSI is widely acknowledged for its effectiveness, greater emphasis on individualized learning strategies can further optimize its impact.
2. The study concludes that observation-based assessment is the most effective and widely used approach for evaluating numeracy skills among students with autism in multisensory instruction. By observing students' engagement and application of mathematical concepts in real-time, educators can make informed decisions about instructional effectiveness. Checklists and rubrics complement this approach by providing a structured evaluation method, while student feedback during hands-on activities further supports comprehension analysis.
3. The study underscores the importance of multisensory instruction as a valuable teaching approach for enhancing numeracy skills in children with autism. By integrating visual, tactile, and auditory elements into their lessons, teachers provide students with diverse and engaging ways to grasp mathematical concepts. This method not only improves comprehension but also fosters active participation, reduces behavioral challenges, and nurtures emotional and social growth. Through MSI, educators create a supportive learning environment that respects each child's unique needs, enabling them to develop confidence and thrive academically.
4. The proposed intervention "A+SLIDES" aligns with the study's findings and offers a promising approach to enhancing numeracy skills among children with autism. By using interactive digital tools that engage multiple senses, it makes learning math more accessible and enjoyable. The tool's simplicity ensures that teachers can easily implement it, while its flexibility caters to the diverse needs of students. Ultimately, this intervention fosters an inclusive learning environment where children with autism can engage with numeracy at their own pace, supporting both academic and emotional growth through the benefits of multisensory instruction.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. To maximize the benefits of multisensory instruction, teachers may continue to explore and innovate their methods to cater to diverse learning styles. Professional development opportunities focused on multisensory teaching and assessment may be provided to

equip educators with the skills and tools they need. Schools may also invest in resources like manipulatives and interactive materials to support these strategies.

2. Teachers may integrate multisensory instructional techniques into their teaching practices to support students with autism in developing numeracy skills. Incorporating tactile tools, interactive games, and sensory-appropriate materials can enhance engagement and learning outcomes. Professional training and access to resources like visual aids, manipulatives, and educational technology may be provided to equip teachers with the tools necessary for effective implementation.

3. It is recommended that special education schools in Camarines Norte and beyond provide training and resources to help teachers effectively implement multisensory instruction in their classrooms. Educators may be equipped with tactile materials, visual aids, and auditory tools to enhance lesson delivery and engagement. Incorporating MSI into daily teaching practices can significantly benefit students with autism and other learning needs by making lessons more interactive and inclusive. Furthermore, collaboration with parents and specialists is essential to ensure that MSI strategies align with the unique needs of each child, promoting holistic development and long-term academic success.

4. Future researchers are encouraged to explore the long-term impact of multisensory instruction on children with autism, particularly across different subjects and age groups. It is also recommended that they examine how collaborative efforts among teachers, parents, and specialists can enhance the effectiveness of this approach. Such investigations may contribute to the development of more inclusive, evidence-based teaching strategies tailored to the diverse needs of learners with autism.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study ensured full compliance with ethical standards throughout the research process. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants after clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained by using pseudonyms and securely storing all data. The interview guide used was validated by experts in Special Education to ensure it was ethical and appropriate for the target respondents. The study adhered to the ethical guidelines set by the institution and ensured that no harm, whether physical or psychological, was inflicted upon the participants during the research.

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REFERENCES

- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Cahapay, M. B. (2022). Efficacy for inclusion and intervention practices of teachers of children with autism in the Philippines. *International Journal of Didactical Studies*, 3(1), 11438. <https://doi.org/10.33902/IJODS.202211438>
- Campado, R. J., Toquero, C. M. D., & Ulanday, D. M. (2023). Integration of assistive technology in teaching learners with special educational needs and disabilities in the Philippines. *International Journal of Professional Development, Learners and Learning*, 5(1), ep2308. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ijpdl/13062>
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2573627>
- De Domenico, C., Di Cara, M., Piccolo, A., Settimo, C., Leonardi, S., Giuffrè, G., De Cola, M. C., Cucinotta, F., Tripodi, E., Impallomeni, C., Quartarone, A., & Cucinotta, F. (2024). Exploring the usefulness of a multi-sensory environment on sensory behaviors in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 13(14), 4162. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm13144162>
- De La Cruz, L. (2020). *The Impact of a Multisensory Intervention on Literacy Attitudes of Students with Dyslexia* (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Texas Rio Grande Valley). <https://www.proquest.com/openview/ef3504374c2dd712477b3eaf1b4d3c57/1?pqorigsite=gscholar&cbl=51922&diss=y>
- Delport, D. (2021). The impact of math manipulatives as a multi-sensory teaching technique in statistics. *MUST: Journal of Mathematics Education, Science and Technology*, 6(2), 186–206. <https://doi.org/10.30651/must.v6i2.10168>
- Faunillan, M. A. V. (2023). Multisensory learning approach as strategy in teaching phonological awareness: A guiding tool for kindergarten instruction. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 12, 328–338. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8251488>
- Goya, D. (2023). *Effects of the Concrete-Representational-Abstract Instructional Sequence on Solving Algebraic Equations for Middle School Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Hawai'i at Manoa). <https://www.proquest.com/openview/21f040e8c82727e23c853c2da3281497/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Huda, E., Hawker, P., Cibralic, S., John, J. R., Hussain, A., Mendoza Diaz, A., & Eapen, V. (2024). Screening tools for autism in culturally and linguistically diverse pediatric populations: A systematic review. *BMC Pediatrics*, 24, Article 610. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-024-05067-5>
- Lämsä, J., Hämäläinen, R., Aro, M., Koskimaa, R., & Äyrämö, S. M. (2018). Games for enhancing basic reading and maths skills: A systematic review of educational game design in supporting learning by people with learning disabilities. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 49(4), 596–607. <https://jyx.jyu.fi/bitstream/>

- handle/123456789/59123/1/games%20for%20enhancing%20basic%20reading%20and%20mathsskills%20main%20text.pdf
- Morsanyi, K., van Bers, B. M., McCormack, T., & McGourty, J. (2018). The prevalence of specific learning disorder in mathematics and comorbidity with other developmental disorders in primary school-age children. *British Journal of Psychology*, 109(4), 917-940. https://pureadmin.qub.ac.uk/ws/files/154631447/The_prevalence_of_developmental_dyscalculia_BJP.pdf
- Okroy, Z., Jacob, P. F., Stern, C., Desmond, K., Otto, N., Talbot, C. B., Vargas-Gutierrez, P., & Waddell, S. (2023). Multisensory learning binds neurons into a cross-modal memory engram. *Nature*, 617(7962), 777–784. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06013-8>
- QSR International. (2020). NVivo (Version 12) [Computer software]. <https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo-qualitative-data-analysis-software>
- Unwin, K. L., Powell, G., & Jones, C. R. G. (2022). The use of Multi-Sensory Environments with autistic children: Exploring the effect of having control of sensory changes. *Autism*, 26(6), 1379–1394. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13623613211050176>
- World Health Organization: WHO. (2023). Autism. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/autism-spectrum-disorders>